

ReCreate

Reusing precast concrete for a circular economy

Arlind Dervishaj & Kjartan Gudmundsson

Common data environment development for reuse

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Abstract

The ReCreate project researches reusing precast concrete elements, not originally designed for disassembly, through real-life deconstruction and reuse pilots in four European countries. The purpose of the current report is to develop a Common Data Environment (CDE) model as well as workflow solutions for the ReCreate project to effectively store, share, and exchange data related to precast concrete reuse across the project's country clusters.

The project's CDE was originally established as a project milestone by March 2022. In this deliverable, we present an update with implementation guidelines, including examples of tools and workflows, for the ReCreate CDE. The report substantially develops further from the CDE milestone, which in addition to including a running CDE, introduced related concepts and a comparison of state-of-the-art solutions. Examples are provided for understanding and preparing data to be shared within ReCreate, as well as cross-cluster collaboration. We will support the country clusters in implementing CDE workflows in the activities of ReCreate, however, each country needs to follow the general guidelines of this report and collaborate on the evolving project needs and workflows as ReCreate develops. The benefits of the proposed CDE require an initial effort that is expected to generate better information sharing, productivity, and synergies within ReCreate. The report includes information on research activities related to conference and journal publications.

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1. Introduction

This is the first deliverable of ReCreate Work Package 3 ‘Logistics and Processing’, and it will result in protocols and workflows for data gathering and sharing in a CDE, which relates to all data throughout the value chain.

This includes, for instance, creating digital instances of the physical elements, which enables tracing information for reuse, and connecting to other types of data, such as material passports and documents. Each physical element will be assigned a unique ID and tagged with a tracking technology, such as *radio frequency identification* (RFID). The CDE will support the creation of a *digital inventory* of reusable precast elements from donor buildings (see also Vullings et al. 2022), which will contain the digital elements in an open file format such as Industry Foundation Classes (IFC).

1.1. CDE concept

A Common Data Environment, abbreviated as CDE, is defined in ISO 19650-1 as an ‘*agreed source of information for any given project or asset, for collecting, managing and disseminating each information container through a managed process*’ (International Organization for Standardization, 2018). A note to the definition of CDE in ISO 19650-1 explains further that ‘*a CDE workflow describes the processes to be used and a CDE solution can provide the technology to support those processes.*’

The goal of the ReCreate CDE is to support the different steps of reusing precast concrete illustrated in Figure 1. Data that is created from deconstruction to reuse, and logistics information, can be gathered in the CDE and linked. For example, a BIM object of a precast concrete element can be linked to its material passport, a unique object ID, and laboratory test results.

Figure 1. Process for the reuse of precast concrete elements in ReCreate.

The traditional way of exchanging project information (e.g., paper, digitized documentation, emails) is a one-to-one relationship where information is exchanged between two or more actors. The traditional method can result in time lost due to: (1) the required numerous exchange efforts, (2) the information is in different places, and/or (3) the information is not organized, structured, in a usable format, or it is not up-to-date. Figure 2 shows the essential difference between traditional information sharing and centralized sharing through a CDE.

Figure 2. Traditional information sharing versus the CDE approach. Source: BIM Portal¹

The CDE approach can benefit collaboration within ReCreate, in particular its country clusters, as data is accessible based on roles and permissions to view, edit, or manage information. A CDE, as a **'single source of truth'**, should allow for queries of information and effective use. This means that information needs to be indexed and retrievable, through the file name, its metadata or assigned tags. The ISO 19650 explains the metadata that needs to be included in the CDE:

1. A revision code, following an agreed standard, for example, IEC 82045-1. Revision codes could be intended for (a) the file, and (b) drawing sheets of the project (e.g., inside a Revit file). In addition, codes can be (a) managed automatically in a CDE when changes happen to an existing file and its metadata, and (b) within files e.g., automation workflow in Dynamo for Revit for revising project documentation. However, the definition and use of revision codes are beyond the purpose of the current deliverable.

2. A status code, showing the permitted use(s) of information. There are four general states outlined in ISO 19650-1 (Figure 3) which are: **work in progress (WIP)**, **shared**, **published**, (i.e.

¹ <https://bimportal.scottishfuturestrust.org.uk/level2/stage/1/task/2/determine-the-info-management-cde-strategy>

approved), and **archived**. There are different means to achieve this: (a) folder structures within a CDE solution, (b) an extension to the file name, and (c) different CDEs for each information state (e.g., WIP information is stored only on the individual CDE of each country cluster, and when data is approved for a milestone delivery, it is shared in the CDE).

3. A naming convention agreed upon among parties who produce, manage, and disseminate information into new forms or deliverables. A naming convention is presented in Section 3.2.

Figure 3. CDE concept diagram from ISO 19650-1.

When accepting and sharing information with external sources, security becomes imperative. In a collaborative and secure CDE, permissions and rights are assigned based on whether a user is internal (employee or team member) or external (e.g., supply chain, consultant).

Some benefits of the CDE approach in ReCreate include:

- Facilitate collaboration between members.
- Avoid duplication.
- Keeping information current.
- Time saved locating documents.
- Uninterrupted usage across devices and locations.
- Version control of files.
- Control of user access and permissions, such as viewing and editing files.

- Document history through metadata, e.g. the last time it was opened, who made changes, what is the revision number, how to find the document in queries through metadata, and how to link the document to other documents, such as a material passport, with a digital model.

2. Developing a CDE

2.1. CDE structure

Work in Progress (WIP) state means that each ReCreate **country cluster (CC)** produces data that can be stored and managed on a local machine or an existing CDE solution that is provided by each organization to their staff. Information is then approved locally and shared in the **ReCreate CDE**, hosted by project coordinator Tampere University in Microsoft Teams. The ReCreate CDE corresponds to the Shared state (Figure 3) and is also shown in Figure 4. In addition, folders with access only to selected members in the ReCreate CDE can be used as a WIP state, in case needed. The WIP CDE is used to develop work such as draft papers and reports, under development BIM objects, and reference material (i.e., other documents that act as guiding references, such as relevant published papers, drawings of existing buildings, old and new pictures of the project, pre-demolition BIM models, etc.).

Construing an open database of precast systems and their constituent parts in ReCreate's Work Package 1 (WPI) relate to the development of the CDE. For example, the deliverable '*D1.4 database with digital models*' will also be transferred to the Shared state (ReCreate CDE) when complete, or filled in progressively, as digital elements become available. **Each CC must produce structured data according to guidelines in the following sections, including naming convention, classification systems, file formats, and object properties.**

The ReCreate CDE may be supported by a **Data Integration** solution (introduced in Figure 4), to facilitate the creation of new object instances with a **unique ID, indexing** of objects for retrieval, and **exchange** of data between CDEs within CCs, the ReCreate CDE, and in modelling tools. For example, the structuring of elements from the WPI deliverable '*D1.3 Taxonomy of precast concrete*' can be used as **tags** to filter and retrieve different types of objects available e.g., precast walls, or precast walls of a particular prefabricated system, and/or walls with specific dimensions.

Looking beyond the limited project-focused perspective of a CDE where there a project-based approved information by the client, it is worth emphasizing its potential for facilitating knowledge sharing and collaboration. This is particularly relevant in the case of research projects such as ReCreate, where sharing data can yield valuable insights for the construction sector and contribute to the dissemination of research findings. For instance, technical reports and deliverables stored in a CDE can be made accessible to relevant stakeholders. The **Published state** is representative of the dissemination of research findings through publications and social media posts. In the context of ReCreate, information can be considered ready for publishing when approved by both CCs and ReCreate consortia, such as in the case of the journal and conference articles. Furthermore, the sharing of **BIM objects**, such as reusable precast elements, in **digital marketplaces** can be regarded as a form of published research output, making these resources readily available to other researchers and practitioners.

To ensure that completed deliverables are properly archived throughout the project and for a designated period following its completion, ReCreate, like many research projects, needs to have a Data Management Plan. The data management plan can be considered the equivalent of the **Archived state** in ISO 19650. Furthermore, we aim to adhere to the largest extent possible to sharing our work under open science principles and the **FAIR guiding principles of scientific data** (Wilkinson et al., 2016), to make our research outputs *findable, interoperable, accessible, and reusable (FAIR)* by whoever may find it useful in their work. For example, archived data would entail as-built BIM models of the donor buildings and the realised pilots, the material passport, environmental product declarations of reused concrete, and any documentation useful for the future renovation, deconstruction and reuse of buildings and their materials.

Figure 4. High-level CDE concept and activities in ReCreate.

2. 2. CDE workflows and solutions

A subsequent diagram of Figure 4 is presented in Figure 5 where *placeholder CDE states* have been substituted with more detailed *workflows* and *solutions* (tools). General-purpose CDEs placed inside the rectangle for the WIP CDE (e.g., Dropbox, OneDrive), or construction sector solutions (e.g., Autodesk Construction Cloud, Egnyte) can act as CC CDEs. Afterwards, the information is copied to the ReCreate CDE. First, templates of **BIM objects** of precast concrete will be developed and shared in a CDE following the **Taxonomy of precast components** with information fields. Subsequently, gathered information from real-world precast elements will be added to the empty fields of the template, which transitions the templates towards a digital twin of selected precast elements for reuse. The objective should not be to map every imaginable property but to define clear guidelines for the templates and only add information that is considered relevant based on the reuse

scenario and/or the research purpose. In addition, objects need to be classified, follow a naming convention, and include properties inherited from the 'as-built model' (e.g. object location in the donor building, construction year, address, function), and properties that come from data integration of various sources (e.g. link to an Environmental Product Declaration, material passport, concrete scanning, and laboratory tests). Annex 1 gives a comparison of different available CDEs for reference.

Figure 5. CDE workflows and solutions in more refined details following the CDE concept in Figure 4.

2.2.1. Data integration

Data integration of various sources includes the unique ID (hereby called the **Taxonomy ID**) of the physical elements (which are different from the ID of authoring tools, e.g. IFC GUID, or Revit element ID), **laboratory tests** (e.g. carbonation, harmful substance contamination, etc.), and **tracking tags** (e.g. RFID attached to elements). Moreover, **indexing** of elements in databases will be done through the naming convention and metadata of BIM objects allowing querying and filtering, to find the needed information, e.g. the right taxonomical object with suitable geometrical, mechanical, and technical properties for reuse. **Avail** (n.d.) is a tool that fulfils some of the requirements outlined in Figures 4 and 5, such as:

- (1) creating content libraries of objects, and finding structured data (e.g. objects based in a country, for a construction system, or every wall element),
- (2) indexing elements from various sources (e.g. user computers and CDEs),
- (3) integrating data from the CDEs shown in Figure 5,
- (4) assigning tags derived from the taxonomy structure (D1.3) to each file,
- (5) subsequently using such tags to retrieve elements, thus using Avail as a database for D1.4,
- (6) exporting/importing elements through the Avail plugins for Revit and Rhino, and

(7) adding links to Avail that point to the Material/Circularity Passport of each element (or a database of material/circularity passports hosted in a more suitable platform for such purpose).

With regards to data management (the 'Archived state' as explained earlier), the website of ReCreate could be hosted for a sufficient amount of time after the completion of activities to make public deliverables available. In addition, role-based access on the website could host internally shared and archived materials, as well as through MS Teams and Avail. Furthermore, each institution is encouraged to make progressive use of its institutional digital repositories, and inform other ReCreate members of it, for finding information.

3. CDE workflows with examples

3.1. File Formats

‘Digital marketplaces’ typically include digital models of construction products in a few proprietary file formats for BIM software, Computer-Aided Design (CAD) formats, and non-proprietary file formats like the IFC. To enable collaboration and effective sharing and dissemination, the templates, or the digital twins, would benefit if they were prepared for CAD, BIM, and open file formats, to make sharing accessible for ReCreate partners and the broader community of researchers and practitioners. **In this regard, we recommend that the ReCreate CCs prepare (1) a BIM object in a native file format (e.g Revit), (2) a CAD object with properties/attributes (e.g in Rhino 3D), and (3) convert the native BIM object to an IFC.** Other documents and file formats, such as PDFs and text documents can be stored in the WIP or Shared CDE. We recommend following the guidelines given in section 3.2 for naming BIM objects and documents.

3.2. Naming conventions

In ISO 19650, the **information container** (i.e. file or data within a file) can also be used to describe the unique ID of the data. This can be done either through (a) the **filename** itself, (b) the **metadata** of the file, or (c) the metadata that is managed/created in the **document management system** of the CDE. Naming conventions are needed when sharing data. Different conventions are possible. An example following an industry guideline is presented in Figure 6, coming from the Scottish context. This is a valid approach, and each country cluster can follow it in their work. Additionally, a convention and example for Sweden are given, which can be used also in the CCs for BIM objects. If another convention is put forward in another CC, it should be sufficiently documented and accompany the folder in the ReCreate CDE.

Figure 6. Example of Naming Convention according to BS EN ISO 19650-1. Source: BIM Portal²

² Retrieved Feb 25, 2022, from <https://bimportal.scottishfuturestrust.org.uk/level1/stage/8/task/47>

In a naming convention, each naming field is given a code to be used. In ReCreate, we target a simple convention that can be easily understood by users. A more simple convention than the one presented in Figure 6, can be used for BIM objects in Sweden:

<Originator>_<CountryCode>_<OriginatorCity/Factory><YearBuilt>_<TaxonomyClass>_<TaxonomyType>_<InstanceNumber>_<Revision>

Example of the adopted naming convention: **KTH_SE_HSBG_1967_Wall_V01_1_0**

Other fields that could be added to the naming convention are the date and suitability (i.e. CDE status). However, the date (date of creation/changes) can be found in the metadata of each file and is visible in CDEs. The status (e.g. work in progress, published) can be managed through the folders of the CDE. When the status code is not managed through the CDE, it can be added to the naming of the file. Other properties of interest can be found in the BIM object or Material/Circularity Passport, or by referring to the Taxonomy structure and classification system. Table 1 provides the nomenclature for field codes. The fields of Table 1 can be defined and completed by each CC. These fields should be used in the creation of digital templates to facilitate the understanding for users.

Table 1. Codes for fields in the naming convention. Notes: (*) if known.

Country	Country code	City / System* / Manufacturer*	Taxonomy class (written in full)	Taxonomy types to be defined
Sweden	SE	Helsingborg / Skåne	Wall, Slab, Beam, Column, Staircase, Connection	V01...etc.
Finland	FI		CC decides / from Taxonomy WPI	
Germany	DE		as above	
Netherlands	NL		as above	

3. 3. Folder structure

Organising files into respective folders for each cluster will be done in WIP and shared CDEs. Figure 7 shows how to find and add data in the Shared folder, with the example of WIP CDE in Sweden. The folders for each country cluster have been created inside the WP3 channel in Teams. The Swedish folder has started to be used and can be accessed through the 'WP3 channel', in the 'ReCreate CDE', inside 'Sweden – shared state'.

Figure 7. Examples of WIP CDE at KTH using OneDrive, and Shared CDE within the Teams Channel.

3. 4. Exchange of data

A **material/circularity passport** is needed to hold information on each physical element to be reused. The simplest solution is to have a list of objects with properties in an Excel file. The material/circularity passport holds information for each element such as a unique ID (i.e. Taxonomy ID – file name – naming convention), test results, and information on attached tags (e.g. QR codes, RFID). Avail or another equivalent solution will be used to index BIM objects and other relevant documents. The documents can be stored in WIP, Shared CDE, or Published CDE, and still be indexed and accessed by users through the ‘Avail Desktop application’, which allows indexing and access of files for different users. Objects can be indexed in Avail by dragging and dropping from the computer desktop, including CDE folders from the desktop, and direct CDE integrations with Avail, but not from web browsers, e.g. dragging from the OneDrive webpage to Avail. However, automatic copying to MS Teams is not possible through any CDEs or Avail at the current moment. Thus, files need (1) to be **copied from the WIP CDE to MS Teams (shared)**, and (b) **indexed from CDEs to Avail**.

In Figure 8, the interface of the desktop application of Avail is shown, with some files added to the ReCreate CDE channel, as well as an example of dropping an element to Revit where it is possible to select any of the different types of a Revit family, as well as check the object properties. The filters/tags are indicated in the lower left part of the image (Avail for desktop screenshot), which includes file extensions, the Revit category and specific keywords assigned when objects are added to the Avail database. The filters/tags can be used for quick retrieval of any file/data as the Avail channel may grow with many BIM objects and documents generated from ReCreate. It is worth noting that Avail does not store objects in the cloud, but objects remain in user computers or CDEs. This is the free plan of Avail, which has a limit of 1,500 items per channel. Other subscription plans provide more features and cloud-hosting capabilities for items.

Figure 8. Example of the Avail for Desktop interface for ReCreate CDE channel, showing a Material Passport, two Revit template objects, and ReCreate logo, and selection of an object in the Avail plugin in Revit.

3. 5. Example of BIM object properties

BIM objects will need to adhere to the country's Taxonomy and classification system, IFC entity, naming convention, and a set of properties. An example of some relevant properties is given in Figure 9. Properties included are Taxonomy ID, Revit family, classification system, e.g. CoClass (Svensk Byggtjänst, 2022), IFC entity, year of construction, year of deconstruction, carbonation depth, count of elements in the BIM model, manufacturer, URL of the template BIM object, and volume.

Generic Model Schedule										
Taxonomy ID	Family	CoClass v3.2.0	IFC 4.3	Construction Year 1st cycle	DeConstruction Year	Carbonation	Count	Manufacturer	URL	Volume
V4-B-C		AD13 Vaggkonstruktion med solid stomme av prefabricerade element av betong	lfcWall	1967	2022	<varies>	64	HSBG	https://kth-my.sharepoint.com/:u:/g/personal/arinddug_kth_s/EVkc0hLkV9Es_XIQi-M6kBR0nXxZBv-l-0JTxMktgvv?e=2krv5D	1.88 m³
P8B		AQ Golvkonstruktion	lfcSlab	1967	2022	<varies>	17	HSBG	https://kth-my.sharepoint.com/:u:/g/personal/arinddug_kth_s/EVkc0hLkV9Es_XIQi-M6kBR0nXxZBv-l-0JTxMktgvv?e=2krv5D	2.42 m³

Figure 9. Revit schedule of a wall and floor type in Revit.

Each object in Revit is assigned a unique ID. This can be retrieved and used to manage objects and parameters in Revit. However, **Revit's unique ID is model-specific**. The Revit ID will change if the object is copied into another digital model. Therefore the use of an ID of physical objects (Taxonomy ID) is a software-agnostic and better solution for the BIM objects that will be developed, starting from the templates of the Taxonomical prefabrication systems, towards digital twins of physical elements selected for reuse. An example of retrieving Revit element IDs is given in Figure 10.

Figure 10. Retrieving the element ID of Revit objects through the Manage tab and inquiry section.

3. 6. Linked BIM data

Data needs to be exchanged between various sources and file types, e.g. between material/circularity passports and BIM models. This can be achieved using **structured data**. Since a BIM model is also a **database**, it is frequently used to extract quantities of materials in an automated way for cost estimation. Schedules of BIM objects and properties can be generated in BIM software tools; however, the workflows may be different.

To give an example, a schedule of BIM objects with properties and material quantities can be created in Revit. Schedules can be exported through the **DiRoots** plugin **SheetLink**, which exports an excel file of e.g. model categories in Revit, or schedules of selected properties in Revit. The exported sheet can be stored in the cloud in a WIP folder. Afterwards, the spreadsheet can be easily modified and populated with data from different sources, e.g. through Google Sheets in the cloud instead of the Revit schedule, and imported back into Revit. This workflow allows updating Revit schedules, that in turn update the information in the digital model. In addition, data can be copied to other sources, starting from the BIM model through the use of schedules and excel spreadsheets, into other data repositories. Furthermore, the cells of a region in an excel spreadsheet can be linked/copied to other cells in the same file or another file. In this way, data can be semi-automatically updated when changes are made, for a specific workflow, and imported through DiRoots in Revit, or vice versa to another data source, e.g. a material/circularity passport.

It is important to be aware and define beforehand what information the CC and consortium consider as WIP, Published, or Shared when exchanging data between models, documents, and public services. Furthermore, some workflows can also be done using **IFC**. For example,

an IFC file can be viewed directly on the web through the **DiStellar** website of DiRoots. The app allows exporting and importing of data stored in the IFC model to an excel spreadsheet, like in the SheetLink workflow for Revit. An example of the described linked data workflows is given in Figure 11. It may be a good choice to use the Revit model for WIP workflows and to use the IFC for exchanging data for Shared and Published state workflows.

Figure 11. Bidirectional data exchange between BIM objects in the Revit model through the Sheetlink plugin which exports an excel spreadsheet to Google Drive, and can reimport the same schedule to make updates to the BIM objects in the project. Material/circularity passports and other sources can be used to semi-automatically exchange data with the spreadsheet in the CDE and with the BIM model.

3. 7. Level of Information Need

The *level of information need (LOIN)* is a new approach to managing and producing information when working with BIM. LOIN was introduced as a concept in ISO 19650 part 1, and later approved as a European standard with EN 17412 part 1 (European Committee for Standardization (CEN), 2020). LOIN is defined as a ‘*framework which defines the extent and granularity of information*’. LOIN provides guidelines for sharing information when using BIM. We will provide further guidance on LOIN in the coming months. In the meantime, CCs can develop CAD, BIM and IFC templates of precast concrete elements following the guidelines in this document and propose any additional approaches and specifications that they are following or considering aligning to based on their experience and local contexts. The comparison of approaches between clusters regarding e.g. classification systems, IFC properties, BIM tools and modelling, can be explored in the upcoming workshops.

4. Classification systems

A classification system (**CS**) is a standard terminology to **manage information in a project**. The use of a CS is a requirement in the ISO 19650 series of standards. The classification of objects allows for consistency and a **'common language'** among professionals and organizations. In addition, classifying building components in a standardized way is a step in organizing **product libraries**, thus relevant also for **libraries for the reuse of objects**. **Therefore, the development of classification/taxonomy in the context of reuse for ReCreate is needed, which allows for a clear description of the functional, geometrical, or technical characteristics of precast elements.**

Classification schemes have been developed in different countries for different purposes. As a result, the same collection of objects can be classified with different criteria and produce different taxonomical structures of elements. In this deliverable, we do not suggest one classification for all ReCreate CCs. Local classifications may exist in the ReCreate countries, and the objective is to have structured models that can be understood in the context of a classification system and the Taxonomy from WPI.

It is recommended that each CC **maps each digital object to their local scheme** if available, to the one of their choice, or relies on the classification scheme of another ReCreate country. In Sweden, we will be classifying objects according to the Swedish **CoClass 2022** system. In addition to the local mapping, each CC should map its objects to the corresponding **IFC entities**. For this purpose, the **buildingSmart Data Dictionaries (bSDD)** can be used (buildingSMART International, n.d.-a), to find the corresponding IFC entity. The bSDD is an online service that has several classifications, definitions (e.g. what is a wall, what does the term mean across selected languages), and a set of properties for each definition. The bSDD can be used to link content between classifications, definitions and standardised properties (buildingSMART International, n.d.-b). The bSDD has an extensive list of properties for each definition. An example of **WALLS in bSDD** is provided in Figure 12. We recommend including only properties that are considered relevant to the reuse scenario and research objectives from the bSDD, and not adding everything to the digital templates.

Figure 12. Query for walls in the bSDD where IFC entities, classification, and properties can be found.

4. 1. Classification of prefabricated concrete in the Swedish context

Next, we aim to present an initial classification for prefabricated concrete systems. The scheme is based on **four criteria** defined in a previous study (Afsari & Eastman, 2016):

Criteria 1 – Purpose and properties of the classification system.

The purpose is to classify precast concrete elements in Sweden. The classification system should be useful to organize elements in a taxonomical structure based on their function, as well as according to a particular construction system.

Criteria 2 – Framework of the system.

The presented classification aims to follow ISO 12006-2 (International Organization for Standardization (ISO), 2015) framework for the classification of building construction products, for geometrical, functional, technical, and cost purposes. In addition, mapping to IFC entities using bSDD will be done.

Criteria 3 – Grouping principles within the system.

Two types of grouping principles in classification are (a) **enumerated** i.e. hierarchical, or (b) **faceted**. A hierarchical grouping cannot add new objects and requires regular revision to accommodate new objects. In a faceted classification, one or multiple sub-classes (or attributes) can be combined to create new classes of concepts. Although prefabricated concrete systems of existing buildings have been defined at the respective time of production and construction, reusing elements would necessitate in some instances measures, such as cutting elements, reusing them for a new application, or new connectors for reassembly. Therefore, a faceted classification system may be more appropriate for precast concrete elements in design for reuse. The motivation for a faceted system also draws from the previous learning experience of the Swedish ReCreate reuse pilot in Helsingborg in 2022. An explanation of why a faceted classification was needed in the Swedish pilot is given in Figure 13.

Figure 13. Example of the Swedish ReCreate reuse pilot where elements from a donor building of the Skåne system, other buildings and factory reject hollow core slabs were utilized.

Criteria 4 – Organization and Taxonomies of Tables.

For the scheme to be exhaustive and definite, objects in a classification system need to belong to only one node (class) in the taxonomy and be distinguishable from other objects. Subdivision criteria of elements or building composition can be based e.g. on geometrical shape, construction material, or functional properties (load-bearing, or building systems). Since we are focusing on a specific system/material (i.e., **prefab concrete**), an element classification based on geometrical shape and functional properties is given in Figure 14. Elements are decomposed into sub-classes up to the level that was possible to identify at the time of writing. For one class of objects, staircases, only one sub-class exist, while walls have three sub-classes. The last level of each class is the type, which is the level that includes the physical objects' geometrical dimensions and other relevant instance properties. The sub-class for types is denoted by a dashed line pointing to its upper class for each element. For more information, please refer to ISO 12006-2 Section 4.2 (classification and composition).

Figure 14. Classification hierarchy for prefabricated concrete based on physical (i.e., geometrical shape) and functional properties.

Another way to classify objects is by following a **compositional hierarchy** e.g. the **prefab system**, or the **MEP building systems** (i.e., mechanical, electrical, and plumbing systems). The Mechanical system includes heating, ventilation, and air conditioning (HVAC). Electrical systems include lighting, power distribution, and communications. Plumbing systems include the water supply system, fixtures and faucets, hot water supply system and drainage system. Precast elements are part of the structural system or the envelope system

and need to accommodate other building systems through openings and installation channels e.g. light and ventilation (i.e. through a window), and building systems that cross rooms, apartments, and floors. However, the decomposition presented in Figure 15 includes only precast concrete elements and their attributes concerning this composition, not actual MEP objects.

Compositional hierarchy – structure (functional/assembly aspect)

Compositional hierarchy – building systems

Figure 15. Example of compositional hierarchy based on the functional assembly of the Skåne crosswall construction frame system, and one hierarchy based on building systems.

In addition, Annex A of ISO 12006-2 gives examples of class table titles. Classification principles that are relevant for precast concrete are:

- A.2 Construction information (by content)
 - by geometry
 - by specification
- A.3 Construction products (by function, form, material, or any combination)
 - structural and space division products
 - general purpose civil engineering and construction fabric product

Classed by material

- cement-based products
- A.8 construction complexes
 - industrial
 - administrative
 - educational
 - residential (and potentially other types of complexes)
- A.9 Construction entities (by form, function, user activity, or combination)
 - buildings
 - prefabricated buildings

Classes (by combination of form, function, and user activity)

- school buildings
- houses

- residential buildings (and other types of buildings)
- A.10 Built spaces (e.g. spaces for living, work, etc.)
- A.11 Construction elements
 - Classes (by function)
 - Floor construction system
 - Wall construction system
 - Roof construction system
 - Classes (by combination of position and form)
 - Substructure: pile
 - Superstructure: slab, wall, beam, column, roof
- A.12 Work results (pre-design work; design work; production work)
- A.13 construction properties
 - Physical properties
 - Functional properties
 - Structural performance
 - Mechanical performance
 - Fire performance
 - Thermal performance
 - Environmental performance
 - spatial and temporal properties
 - shape, size
 - time e.g. carbonation, chlorination, service life

The propositions of classification in this chapter introduced classifying precast concrete for reuse. Classification can be the scope of a future ReCreate workshop to reach an agreement and define class tables, names, and structures. The classification could be used to (a) improve/expand on the naming convention, (b) name objects in the BIM model (e.g., Family and Type in Revit), and (c) combine or use in conjunction with the local classification (e.g., CoClass). Moreover, Section B.4 in ISO 12006 describes two strategies for representing objects in modelling tools:

- a) replace the starting object (a generic wall or the template) with specialised BIM objects (e.g. a precast element, a digital twin of a reused object).
- b) keep original objects by adding sub-class properties and further refine the class properties of the BIM object.

When the starting model is a point cloud from a laser scanning or an existing drawing, BIM objects can be modelled following one of these as modelling references. If the 3D model is created using basic objects in BIM software, the generic elements (walls, floors, columns etc.) can be substituted with the digital templates of precast elements. Then, the templates are filled with information as data becomes available. It can also be the case that the location of panels is known from drawings, or precast elements are exposed and visible in pictures and from the point clouds. In this case, digital templates can be used directly to create the as-built model.

5. Interoperability

BIM Dictionary (n.d.) provides the following definition for interoperability:

'The ability of diverse systems (and organisations) to work together seamlessly without data loss and without a special effort. Interoperability may refer to systems, processes, file formats, etc. Interoperability is not synonymous with openness. For example, interoperable file formats can be proprietary-closed (e.g. RVT), proprietary-open (e.g. DWF) and non-proprietary (e.g. IFC).'

It is common in project-based work to experience data loss due to different file formats, unstructured data, and knowledge which is held in the minds of experts and believed to be tacit and not transferable in computer systems. Therefore, interoperability without data loss or effort is difficult to implement and realise in practice. In Figure 16, an example of interoperability between tools and file formats is given. While exchanging data through file formats is still common, new interoperability solutions are more frequently used in project-based work, such as using Application Programming Interfaces (API) to exchange data between tools, and/or solutions like Rhino.Inside, which allows loading Rhino as a plugin inside of Revit, and cloud platforms, e.g. Speckle (for sharing data across a variety of digital tools).

Figure 16. Mapping of interoperability & collaboration in digital design & sustainable construction.

6. Conclusions

ReCreate's Shared CDE has been running on Tampere University's MS Teams since the beginning of the project. The current deliverable presented a developing CDE for ReCreate following the ISO 19650 series of standards. Specific CDE workflows and solutions are given and available for use immediately to ReCreate members. Specific examples of CDE workflows are provided for naming, sharing, and retrieving information in a CDE. In addition, the deliverable explains how to create structured data and integrate data from various sources such as laboratory tests, tracking technologies, a unique ID of precast elements, and material/circularity passports. Guidelines are provided for naming conventions, folder structure, BIM object properties, information exchange, and linked data across BIM models and other sources of information. The use of templates for BIM objects based on the taxonomy of precast elements from WP1, classification systems, element IDs, and assigned metadata is demonstrated with examples.

The report proposes a faceted classification system for precast concrete, that in turn supports new applications for the design for reuse and enables the unique identification of elements (Taxonomy ID) in the database, as well as assigning digital tags. The precast classification should be used in combination with the local classification e.g. CoClass. A comprehensive overview of CAD and BIM tools and their interoperability is presented in the last section. The CDE workflows and solutions aimed to achieve not only sharing of files but sharing of databases and the utilisation of applications for integrating information from different sources, and enhancing collaboration within ReCreate. Secondly, the aim is to enable the effective dissemination of selected research outputs. The presented findings are part of our ongoing research efforts towards conference and journal publications.

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Annex 1. Comparison of CDEs.

BIM modelling software companies (e.g., Autodesk, Graphisoft) have introduced their CDE tools for the construction sector. Alternative CDEs include Google Drive, Dropbox, and OneDrive, which may be already available and provided to ReCreate members in their respective institutions. The following table gives an overview of the features we selected to consider when adopting a CDE. Popular cloud solutions and specific CDEs built for the AEC industry are represented. The table can be helpful to each cluster when considering the adoption of a work-in-progress CDE.

Criteria	DALUX						
Storage space	Unlimited	Unlimited	15 GB Free, Google One Basic 100 GB, Standard 200 GB, Premium 2TB	Free, variable plans & users	2Gb Free, variable plans >1Tb	10 Gb free, variable plans	Not clear
Applications	BIM functionalities, integrations	BIM functionalities, integrations	Google Docs, Sheets, Slides, Drawings, Boards	Dropbox Paper	Office 360	BIM functionalities, integrations	-
Document Management System (DMS)	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
File types recognized	Limited	Limited	Unlimited from Windows app folder	Unlimited from Windows app folder	Unlimited from Windows app folder	Limited	Limited
User access & user permissions	Yes	Yes	Yes, not project based	Yes	Yes, not project based	Yes	Yes
Version control	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes (for Business)	Yes	Yes
File viewers	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
IFC support	Yes	Yes	No	No	No		Yes
BCF support	Yes	Yes	No	No	No	Yes	Yes
GDPR acceptance	Yes (link)	Yes (link)	Yes (link)	Yes (link)	Yes (link)	Yes (link)	Yes, partial (link)
Subscription / Capex cost	Yes	Yes	No, scalable	No, scalable	No, scalable	No, scalable	Not clear, individual fees or project fees
Local server / VPN connection need	No	No	No	No	No	No	No
Multi-factor authentication	No	No	Yes	Yes	Yes	No	No
Backup and restore	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes